

Supporting Material

Specific engineered G protein coupling to histamine receptors revealed from cellular assay experiments and accelerated molecular dynamics simulations

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Figure S1. Comparison of the structural flexibility in H₂R and H₄R complexes with mini-G proteins. A) Overall structural flexibility (RMSF) of the H₂R-mGs complex and changes in structural flexibility (Δ RMSF) in the H₂R complexes, when mGs was exchanged by mGsi (B) or mGsqs (C). D) Overall structural flexibility (RMSF) of the H₄R-mGsi complex and changes in structural flexibility (Δ RMSF) in the H₄R complexes, when mGsi was exchanged by mGs (E) or mGsqs (F). For RMSFs, a color scale of 0.0 Å (blue) to 4.0 Å (red) was used. In case of Δ RMSF, the color scale ranged from -1.0 Å (blue) to 1.0 Å (red). (Δ)RMSF values were assigned to the starting structure of each system.

Figure S2. Time courses of the reaction coordinates in H₂R systems (H₂R-mGs, H₂R-mGsi and H₂R-mGsq) used for energetic reweighting. A) Distance between D^{3.32} and histamine (HSM) using the CG atom of D^{3.32} and N α of histamine. B) Distance between TM3 and TM6 of the H₂R. The C α , C and N atoms of residues R^{3.50} and E^{6.30} were used to calculate the distance. C) Distance between the NPxxY motif and α 5 helix of the respective mini-G protein. The distance was calculated using the center of mass of the NPxxY motif and the last five residues of α 5 helix. D) Distance between TM2 of the H₂R and the α 5 helix of the respective mini-G protein. To calculate the distance, the C α , C and N atoms of T^{2.39} and the geometric center of the last five residues of α 5 were used.

Figure S3. Time courses of the reaction coordinates in H₄R systems (H₄R-mGs, H₄R-mGsi and H₄R-mGsq) used for energetic reweighting. A) Distance between D^{3.32} and histamine (HSM) using the CG atom of D^{3.32} and N α of histamine. B) Distance between TM3 and TM6 of the H₄R. The C α , C and N atoms of residues R^{3.50} and A^{6.30} were used to calculate the distance. C) Distance between the NPxxY motif and α 5 helix of the respective mini-G protein. The distance was calculated using the center of mass of the NPxxY motif and the last five residues of α 5 helix. D) Distance between TM2 of the H₄R and the α 5 helix of the respective mini-G protein. To calculate the distance, the C α , C and N atoms of S^{2.39} and the geometric center of the last five residues of α 5 were used.

Figure S4. Binding modes of histamine (light blue) within the orthosteric binding pocket of the H_2R (salmon) and the H_4R (purple). Structures representing the separated histamine state “S2” in H_2R -mGs (A), the intermediately bound state “I1” (B) and the separated histamine states “S1” (C) and “S2” (D) in H_2R -mGsi, the intermediately bound state “I1” (E) and the separated histamine states “S2” (F) in H_2R -mGsq complexes, as well as the separated histamine state “S1” in the H_4R -mGs complex (G) are shown. Contact residues within 4 Å of the ligand are highlighted as sticks (dark grey). The histamine- $D^{3.32}$ distance is highlighted with a red, dashed line.

Figure S5. Free energy profiles of GaMD simulations with complexes of either the H₂R or the H₄R in combination with mGs, mGsi or mGsq. Distances (Å) between D^{3,32} (CG atom) and the amino group of histamine (N α atom) as well as of the NPxxY - α 5 helix distance were used as reaction coordinates. The NPxxY distance was determined using the center-of-mass (COM) distance between the receptors' NPxxY motif and the last 5 residues of the mG α 5 helix. For each system, three independent GaMD simulations were used for analysis. (Labels: "B" indicates representative low energy wells of fully active receptors bound to histamine, "I1" indicates low energy wells of intermediate receptor conformation bound to histamine. "S1" and "S2" indicate low energy wells containing conformations with histamine separated from D^{3,32}, cf. Figure 1).

Figure S6. Comparison of the $\alpha 5$ helix orientation at the GPCR- G protein interface. Cytoplasmic view of the $\alpha 5$ helix orientation of exemplary A) GPCR-Gs complexes (β_2 AR, pdb-id.: 3SN6, purple; β_1 AR, pdb-id.: 7JJO, light red; D_1 R, pdb-id.: 7CKX, dark green; A_{2A} AR, pdb-id.: 6GDG, light green), B) GPCR-Gi complexes (M_2 R, pdb-id.: 6OIK, purple; D_2 R, pdb-id.: 7JVR, light red; D_3 R, pdb-id.: 7CMU, dark green; α_{2A} AR, pdb-id.: 6K42, light green; A_1 R, pdb-id.: 6DH9, blue) and GPCR-Gq complexes (H_1 R, pdb-id.: 7DFL, purple; M_1 R, pdb-id.: 6OIJ, light red; 5-HT_{2A} R, pdb-id.: 6WHA, dark green). D) Comparison of the $\alpha 5$ helix orientation in the β_2 AR-Gs complex (purple) and the representative structures of low energy wells containing the fully active receptors bound to histamine (“B” states, cf. Fig. 1) of the H_2 R-mGs (light red), H_2 R-mGsi (dark green) and H_2 R-mGsq (light green) complexes obtained in GaMD simulations. The $\alpha 5$ helix orientation in representative histamine bound structures of H_4 R-mGs (“I1” state, light red), H_4 R-mGsi (“B” state, dark green) and H_4 R-mGsq (“B” state, light green) complexes are compared to the E) β_2 AR-Gs (purple) and F) M_2 R-Gi (purple) complexes. The Gs-like $\alpha 5$ orientation towards TM6 is highlighted in red and the Gi-like $\alpha 5$ orientation towards TM2 in pink.

Figure S7. Sequence alignment of the Gas subunit and the utilized mini-G proteins mGs, mGsi and mGsq. Secondary structure elements of Gas, such as α helices and β sheets, are highlighted as loops and arrows, respectively, in blue (GTPase domain) and yellow (helical domain). The switch regions (SWI, SWII and SWIII) are labeled in green. Identical residues of the sequences are colored in light grey. Sequence differences are highlighted due to the chemical properties of the residue functional groups (acidic: red, aliphatic: black, aliphatic (small): grey, amide: green, aromatic: brown, basic: blue, hydroxyl: pink, imino: orange, sulfur: yellow). Residues only present in Gas are not shaded.